

A Critical Analysis of the CO₂ Plank transcritical refrigeration cycle under extreme ambient conditions

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ABSTRACT

Extreme temperature conditions are becoming frequent also in temperate areas. While carbon dioxide is spreading all over the world, as a safe and environmentally friendly refrigerant, there is an increasing need for making CO₂ cycle efficient also under high ambient temperature, while assuring affordability, serviceability and cost competitiveness.

The Plank transcritical cycle involves heat rejection at two different pressure levels: heat is first rejected at a pressure lower than the optimal one of corresponding simple cycle, thus resulting in reduced compression ratio, then pressure is increased by a pump, to meet the optimal rejection pressure as required by the secondary fluid thermal flow capacity.

In this paper, thermodynamic analysis of a CO₂ refrigeration cycle identifies optimal heat rejection pressures under extreme ambient temperature. By numerical simulations the practical implementation of the cycle is critically discussed, considering finite heat rejection exchange areas. Considerations related to the relative sizing of the two gas coolers and comparison with simple compression cycle are presented.

Keywords: Carbon Dioxide; Transcritical Cycle, Plank cycle, Optimal pressure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon dioxide is nowadays the preferred fluid in many applications due to its intrinsic safety characteristics and harmfulness towards the environment and it still retains a large potential to be used in many others. For many years different solutions have been successfully implemented to make CO₂ suitable to work in hot climates, i.e. parallel compression, ejectors for vapour pre-compression, mechanical subcooling, evaporative post-gas cooling and more recently pressure exchanger.

The changing climate is determining on one side the average temperature increase, moving norther the "CO₂ equator" line, and on the other side the more frequent occurrence of heat waves and temperature peaks also in temperate or cold areas. For these reasons it is necessary to identify suitable solutions for overcoming the loss of capacity and inefficiencies of the cycle at extreme ambient conditions. In particular, when referring to heat waves, capacity decrease results to be the most relevant drawback. On the other hand, system oversizing to be ready to cope with potential high temperatures for few hours per year may lead to inefficient operation under the most frequent temperate or cold conditions, thus heavily impacting on overall annual energy consumption, together with increased investment cost. Simple and flexible solutions than can support when needed are then advisable.

The Plank Cycle was patented by Rudolf Plank in 1912 (Plank, 1912): it applies to a transcritical CO₂ cycle, using a compressor to increase the cycle pressure after gas cooling, thus meeting the optimal pressure,

according to ambient temperature, at the expansion valve inlet. The overall solution features a double compression cycle with transcritical intermediate pressure and intercooling down to near-ambient temperature. The expected benefit lies in the decreased compression work as the gas density at the second compression stage suction is high.

Inokuty, 1924, systematically thermodynamically investigated the Plank cycle. He first renamed the second compressor as a “pump” as CO₂ at the considered conditions resembled a liquid more than a gas. Inokuty presented interesting results related to optimal intermediate pressure of the cycle, showing that the intermediate pressure is nearly independent from the evaporation pressure and the pump discharge pressure, given that the intercooler and the gas cooler outlet temperature assume the same value. Being this last value dependent on the cooling fluid temperature, the volume of the pump must be adjustable. The assumption of equal temperature at gas cooler and intercooler exit underlines the fact that the thermodynamic analysis considers ideal heat transfer processes. This aspect will be considered in the present work. Inokuty proposed a possible design for a suitable pump. He finally calculated an expected benefit in terms of COP (at 17.8 bar evaporation pressure and 32.2°C cooling water temperature) equal to 16.8%. Inokuty experimentally measured 18.3% COP improvement and 60.8% capacity improvement by combining the Plank cycle with the Multiple Effect Cycle.

Oestertag and Prior, 1926, calculated the benefit of the Plank Cycle at -20°C evaporation temperature and +37.5°C gas cooler outlet temperature, concluding that the modified cycle can give +6% increase in cooling effect and +40% increase in COP, being 91 bar the compressor discharge pressure for the Plank cycle and 122 bar the discharge pressure for the reference cycle and for the pump discharge pressure of the Plank Cycle. Oestertag and Prior quantified the relative work of the pump with respect to the total work, being 20% under the considered assumptions.

Cecchinato et al., 2009, analysed the Plank cycle classifying it as a double compression cycle, where the intermediate pressure is transcritical. They theoretically explained the limited impact of the second stage compression pressure on the optimal intermediate pressure once that the high-pressure heat exchangers exit temperature is constant, thus confirming Inokuty's findings.

All the above-mentioned works assumed ideal intercooler and gas cooler, i.e. hypothesized that CO₂ can approach ambient temperature according to a pre-set temperature difference whatever the cycle.

To critically highlight Plank Cycle potentialities, this paper explores the impact of components characteristics on the cycle COP and capacity, considering both gas cooler and intercooler size and compressor and pump efficiency. These considerations are propaedeutic to explore possible applications of the cycle itself.

2 THERMODYNAMIC ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION

The aim of the thermodynamic analysis is to provide an initial assessment of the optimal working conditions (optimal pressures) and the corresponding performances (COP and specific cooling capacity) as a function of the sink temperature. The system schematics and pressure-enthalpy cycle are reported in Figure 1, where each thermodynamic state of the cycle is identified by labels.

The assumptions used in these calculations are the following:

- evaporation temperature $T_1 = 0^\circ\text{C}$;
- Regenerative Internal Heat Exchanger (IHX) efficiency $\eta_{ihx} = \frac{T_{1\text{ihx}} - T_1}{T_5 - T_1} = 0.9$;
- ideal gas cooling process (no pressure losses, gas cooler outlet temperature equal to sink temperature);
- pump and compressor efficiencies independent from the operating condition.

Figure 1. Plank cycle: (a) simplified schematic, with compressor, Main Gas Cooler (MGC), pump, Auxiliary Gas Cooler (AGC); High Pressure Valve (HPV) (b) p-h diagram ($T_3 = T_5 = T_{sink} = 45^\circ\text{C}$, $T_6 = T_{source} = 0^\circ\text{C}$).

To have a consistent nomenclature between the Plank cycle and the simple compression cycle, which will act as the baseline, the heat exchanger performing gas cooling between points 2 and 3 will be referred as Main Gas Cooler (MGC), while the heat exchanger performing gas cooling between point 4 and 5 as Auxiliary Gas Cooler (AGC).

Given the sink temperature (i.e. the gas cooler outlet temperature $T_{out\ GC}$) the cycle can be computed for a given couple of pressure p_2 and p_4 (under the assumption $p_4 \geq p_2$) under the listed assumptions. The coefficient of performance and the specific cooling capacity are then computed as:

$$q_p = H_5 - H_{1\ ihx} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$COP_p = \frac{q_p}{(H_2 - H_{1\ ihx}) + (H_4 - H_3)} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

The optimization of the COP is stated as follows:

$$\text{Find } x_{opt} = (p_2, p_4) \text{ i.e. } COP_p(x_{opt}) = \text{argmax}(COP_p(x)), \text{ for a given } T_{out\ GC}, \text{ under the constraints: } p_4 \geq p_2; \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

The optimization problem in Eq. 3 for $T_{out\ GC}$ between 30 and 60°C (5°C step) is solved via Golden search algorithm (Mathworks, 2023).

Performance and operating conditions of simple compression cycle are optimized under the same assumptions, for fair comparison to the Plank cycle performances. In this case the COP and the specific cooling capacity are rearranged accordingly to the simple cycle:

$$q_s = H_3 - H_{1\ ihx} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

$$COP_s = \frac{q_s}{(H_2 - H_{1\ ihx})} \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

The optimization problem formulation (Eq. 3) is in this case simplified, as the only design variable is p_2 :

$$\text{Find } x_{opt} = p_2 \text{ i.e. } COP_s(x_{opt}) = \text{argmax}(COP_s(x)), \text{ for a given } T_{out\ GC} \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

2.1 Ideal case ($\eta_c = 1$, $\eta_p = 1$)

Figure 2 reports the optimum COP and the corresponding operating conditions of the Plank and the simple cycle for different sink temperatures.

Figure 2. Comparison of optimal operating conditions between simple (s) and Plank (P) cycle, as a function of gas cooler outlet pressure, in ideal conditions: (a) discharge pressures; (b) COP and specific cooling capacity.

The optimal pressures (Figure 2a) suggest that the optimal configuration of the Plank cycle is similar to the one of classical transcritical two stage compression system with intercooler. In fact, the intermediate pressure p_2 is close to the harmonic average of the lower and higher pressures (with pressure ratios slightly unbalanced, having the compressor higher pressure ratio than the pump). For $T_{out\ GC} = 30^\circ\text{C}$ the maximum pressure of the Plank cycle is almost equal to the optimal high pressure of the simple cycle (+0.4 bar). The difference between the high pressures of the two cycles slightly increases with the sink temperature reaching +12 bar for $T_{out\ GC} = 60^\circ\text{C}$.

The cycle COP of the Plank cycle (Figure 2b) is systematically higher than the simple cycle (0.5-0.3 points), leading to a relative increase in the COP in the range of +11% to +19%, with higher relative improvement occurring at higher temperatures. The specific cooling capacity of the Plank Cycle is higher than the reference cycle over the whole temperature range. As the high pressure value for the two cycles is similar, the improvement in cooling capacity is negligible at $T_{out\ GC} = 30^\circ\text{C}$ (+1%), while it becomes larger, but still moderate, at higher temperatures (maximum +6% for $T_{out\ GC} = 60^\circ\text{C}$).

2.2 Non-Ideal compression ($\eta_c = 0.75$, $\eta_p = 0.5$)

The assumption of ideal and reversible compressions in Section 2.1 strongly affects all the aspects of the optimization results: the optimal operating conditions, the expected performances and the relative advantages of the Plank cycle over the simple one. For this reason, a second thermodynamic comparison is carried out assuming non-ideal compressions processes.

The compressor efficiency is assumed equal to $\eta_c = 0.75$. This value is representative of standard compressors available on the market. The efficiency of the pump is, on the other side, more difficult to estimate, given the lack of an established market for these components in the specific application. Aakre et al. (2021) report the experimental efficiency of a supercritical CO_2 pump, which can reach hydraulic efficiency up to 52% (the data trend suggest higher efficiencies can be achieved with higher rotational speed and pressure lifts), volumetric efficiency up to 95% and pressure lift up to 33 bar. The test conditions (pressure and temperature) are different from those of the typical Plank cycle, preventing from the direct use of the data. On the other side, the small number of operating conditions (rotational speed, flow rate and pressure lift) reported is too small to derive a parametric model of the unit efficiency. A value of $\eta_p = 0.5$ is then used, assuming that component optimization might be performed

starting from the available models, to align the best efficiency of the unit to the working conditions required by the Plank cycle.

Figure 3 reports the results of the optimization process with $\eta_c = 0.75$ and $\eta_p = 0.5$.

Figure 3. Comparison of optimal operating conditions between simple (s) and Plank (p) cycle, as a function of gas cooler outlet pressure, in non-ideal conditions: (a) discharge pressures; (b) COP and specific cooling capacity.

The implementation of a non-ideal compression in the thermodynamic model significantly affects the results of the optimization process, both in term of expected performances and of optimal operating conditions.

While the optimal pressure of the simple cycle is not affected by the new assumptions, the optimal pressures of the Plank Cycle are strongly impacted. Given the low efficiency of the pump, the optimum cycles rely more on the compressor than on the pump, reducing the pressure ratio between the intermediate and the high pressure. This impacts the optimal cycles, as visible in Figure 4, where the optimal Plank cycles in case of ideal and non-ideal compressions are compared for $T_{out\ GC} = 30^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_{out\ GC} = 45^\circ\text{C}$.

While, as already discussed, the optimal cycle in the case of ideal compression approaches the intercooled two-stage compression cycle (Figure 4a and b), when the compression efficiency is considered, a different behaviour is highlighted. For relatively low sink temperatures ($T_{out\ GC} \leq 35^\circ\text{C}$, Figures 4a and 4c), the intermediate pressure approximates the simple cycle optimal pressure. The pump suction condition (3) is, in this case, on the left side of the saturation dome (liquid region), while it was on the right side (vapour region) in the ideal case. When the compression efficiencies are considered and the sink temperature is high ($T_{out\ GC} = 45^\circ\text{C}$, Figure 4d) the intermediate pressure is lower than the simple cycle high pressure, but not as low as in the ideal compression case. Pump compression starts closer to the critical point.

The comparison between ideal case (Figure 4a and b) and the non-ideal compressions case (Figure 4c and d) demonstrates that in the optimal ideal case most of the heat rejection is performed by the AGC, while the optimal cycle rejects most of the heat in the MGC if the compressor and pump efficiency are considered.

The inclusion of the compression efficiencies, as expected, lowers the absolute value of COP of both the cycles. The Plank cycle still presents an advantage over the simple compression system in terms of COP and specific cooling power. The absolute advantage given by the Plank cycle increases with the gas

cooler outlet temperature from +0.15 to +0.10 points in the range $T_{out GC} = 30 \dots 60^\circ\text{C}$, corresponding to relative increase between 4% and 8%, while the cooling power increases by 6% over the whole temperature range.

Figure 4. Comparison of optimal Simple and Plank Cycles: (a) ideal compression, $T_{out GC} = 30^\circ\text{C}$; (b) ideal compression, $T_{out GC} = 45^\circ\text{C}$; (c) non-ideal compression, $T_{out GC} = 30^\circ\text{C}$; (d) non-ideal compression, $T_{out GC} = 45^\circ\text{C}$.

3 TEST CASE

The cycle application in actual working conditions is discussed considering, as a test case, a chiller serving an AC hydronic loop. The test case will allow to further discuss the impact of real components in the cycle, as the effect of finite heat exchangers will be included in the model.

The system size and main components have been modelled after an actual CO_2 system installed in northern Italy to serve a hotel located in a tourist area. The complete and detailed description of the real installation is reported in Sisti et al. (2023), while the main features of the system are reported here below. The system is designed to include also heat recovery in case of simultaneous needs of cooling and heating, but, for the purpose of this study, operation in simple chiller configuration is considered. The simplified schematic of the baseline unit in chiller configuration is presented in Figure 5a.

The baseline system has a nominal capacity of 150 kW in cooling mode ($12\text{-}7^\circ\text{C}$ cold water), at 36°C ambient temperature. Three compressors in parallel (one with variable speed control, two following an ON/OFF control), are used to allow the necessary flexibility to satisfy the thermal load. The total swept volume of the compressors per unit time is $49.84 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ at 50 Hz ($1450 \text{ rev min}^{-1}$). After compression, the refrigerant mass flow rate rejects heat to the environment in the gas cooler, which is characterized by total internal and external heat exchange surfaces equal to 69.3 m^2 and 525.2 m^2 , respectively. After

expansion, a gravity fed plate evaporator is used in flooded operation, to cool down the water coming from the cold-water tank. The system includes also an additional ejector-driven evaporator which operates at a lower evaporation pressure, where the two-phase ejector provides the pressure lift from evaporation pressure to the liquid receiver pressure. The two evaporators are operated simultaneously at full load conditions.

Figure 5. Simplified schematic of the chiller test case: (a) baseline system; (b) Plank cycle modified system.

Considering the above-described real-life test case as reference, a modification of the baseline cycle is assumed to realize the Plank cycle, as represented in Figure 5b. In this case, a supercritical CO₂ pump is added after the outlet of the Main Gas Cooler, followed by an Auxiliary Gas Cooler.

Different size of the Main Gas Cooler and the Auxiliary Gas Cooler are discussed in this paper. The installed gas cooler is used as reference. The parameters k_{MGC} and k_{AGC} are adopted to scale proportionally all the extensive properties (mass, areas and fans power consumption), while maintaining the same internal geometry of the fin and tube heat exchanger (fin pitch, row and tube pitch).

To obtain a fair comparison, the same components are considered for the simple and Plank cycles. In particular, the same overall size of the gas cooler will be considered between the simple and the Plank cycle: for each sizing of the Plank gas coolers (corresponding to a couple of k_p^{MGC} and k_p^{AGC}) the corresponding size of the simple cycle gas cooler was obtained as the sum of the two:

$$k_s^{MGC} = k_p^{MGC} + k_p^{AGC} \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

4 NUMERICAL MODELLING

The unit is simulated by a dynamic lumped model commercial software (Siemens, 2025). The primary components of the system, including compressors, gas cooler, internal heat exchanger and back-pressure valve, as well as control loops, are modelled using the software's built-in libraries. This acausal approach relies on undirected equations to simulate the transient behaviour of internal and external flows, including refrigerant and ambient air. Each component is represented as a sub-model, constructed by integrating fundamental elements, and the complete cooling system model is subsequently developed by interconnecting these sub-models in accordance with the operational scheme described in Section 3. Each sub-model is governed by nonlinear time-dependent differential equations that define the state variables. These equations are assembled into a system of differential equations, which is subsequently integrated over time to simulate the system's dynamic behaviour. A

detailed description of the numerical approach is beyond the scope of this article and can be found in Artuso et al. (2020), Fabris et al. (2021) and Sisti et al. (2023). Here below the main characteristics and assumptions of the numerical model are reported.

The fin-and-tube air gas coolers (both the main and the auxiliary one in the case of the Plank cycle system) are discretized into nine lumped volumes. Each volume is further subdivided into three nodes corresponding to the refrigerant flow, the tube wall and fins, and the surrounding air. The geometric properties of the heat exchangers, including surface area and mass, are evenly distributed across the lumped elements. The heat transfer processes considered include internal convection between the refrigerant and the internal tube wall, conduction through the tube wall and fins, and external convection between the fins and ambient air. On the other hand, the IHX is discretized into five lumped volumes, each one characterized with two nodes of refrigerant flow (low-pressure and high-pressure sides) and a node of tube wall, accounting for refrigerant convection and conduction through the heat exchanger walls.

As the main focus is the high pressure side of the system, the low pressure side is not modelled. The low pressure is set as a boundary after the High Pressure Valve (HPV) and at the IHX low pressure inlet (where the saturated vapour condition has been set to enforce the physical constrain given by the two-phase low-pressure receiver). According to the assumption done in the thermodynamic analysis, the evaporation temperature of 0°C is considered.

Proportional-Integral controllers are used to regulate the gas cooling pressures. In the baseline system, the gas cooler pressure is controlled acting on the opening ratio of the back-pressure valve, to achieve the set-point value. Similarly, in the Plank cycle system the back-pressure valve controls the Auxiliary Gas cooler pressure (p_4) while the Main Gas Cooler pressure (p_2) is controlled acting on the speed of the transcritical pump.

The compressors are modelled as fixed displacement elements, where the volumetric and the overall compression efficiencies are interpolated from manufacturer data (Dorin, 2024) as a function of pressure ratio and suction pressure. On the contrary, a full performance map of the supercritical pump cannot be compiled due to the lack of experimental data, as discussed in Section 2.2 and, consequently, a constant efficiency equal to $\eta_p = 0.5$ is set as an input of the model.

The power consumption of the compressors is accounted based on these efficiencies:

$$P_I^c = m_I \frac{H_2 - H_{1\text{ihx}}}{(\eta_I^c)} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

where $I = 1..3$ is the index cycling between the three compressors. The same approach is used to compute the pump power consumption:

$$P^p = m^p \frac{H_4 - H_3}{(\eta^p)} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

The model inputs consist of the ambient air temperature and relative humidity, and the set-point gas cooling pressures, as above described. The model outputs encompass the physical state of each state variables, which enable the calculation of heat transfer rates within the heat exchangers and the compressors power consumption.

The optimizations of COP expressed in equations 3 and 6 is solved using the dynamic numerical model to compute the thermodynamic cycle, based on the components and the boundaries. The cooling capacities (Eq. 1 and 4) and COP (Eq. 2 and 5) are in this case defined as follows:

$$Q_s = \sum_{I=1}^3 m_I (H_3 - H_{1\text{ihx}}) \quad \text{with } I = 1..3 \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

$$Q_p = \sum_{I=1}^3 m_I (H_5 - H_{1\text{ihx}}) \quad \text{with } I = 1..3 \quad \text{Eq. (11)}$$

$$COP_s = \frac{Q_s}{P_s^{tot}} \quad \text{Eq. (12)}$$

$$COP_p = \frac{Q_p}{P_p^{tot}} \quad \text{Eq. (13)}$$

where the total power consumptions P_s^{tot} and P_p^{tot} are accounted considering the compressors, the pump and the gas cooler fans power consumption. This last term has been scaled accordingly to the respective k factors:

$$P_s^{tot} = \sum_{l=1}^3 P_l^c + k_s^{MGC} P^{fan} \quad \text{Eq. (14)}$$

$$P_p^{tot} = \sum_{l=1}^3 P_l^c + P^p + (k_p^{MGC} + k_p^{AGC}) P^{fan} \quad \text{Eq. (15)}$$

5 NUMERICAL RESULTS

The optimal working conditions of the Plank cycle have been solved for different sizes of the AGC, assuming the MGC equal to the reference ($k_p^{MGC} = 1$). For each couple of main and auxiliary gas cooler, the optimal performance of the simple cycle using a gas cooler with the same total area (Eq. 7) are solved for reference. All the simulations are carried out considering the unit working at full load, i.e. with the three compressors turned on and running at their nominal speed.

Figures 6 to 8 present the optimal cycles and performance for different size of the auxiliary gas cooler (namely 25, 50 and 100% of the reference gas cooler, i.e. $k_p^{AGC} = 0.25, 0.50$ and 1.00).

When the Auxiliary Gas Cooler is small ($k_p^{AGC} = 0.25$, Figure 6), the Plank cycle is not able to guarantee any performance improvement, except for ambient air temperature higher than 50°C . In fact, for ambient temperature lower than this threshold, the optimal solution overlaps the simple cycle configuration. The auxiliary gas cooler is, in fact, too small to reject enough heat to obtain a positive impact on the system COP.

The increase of the auxiliary gas cooler size allows to reduce the threshold at which the optimal Plank cycle differs from the optimal simple cycle. With $k_p^{AGC} = 0.50$ this limit moves to 40°C (Figure 7), while when the auxiliary gas cooler has the same size of the main gas cooler ($k_p^{MGC} = k_p^{AGC} = 1.00$), the Plank cycle guarantees an improvement on both COP and Cooling Capacity over the whole range of ambient temperatures (Figure 8). Nevertheless, this improvement is hardly appreciable (less than 5%) for ambient temperature lower than 40°C . In fact, the advantage of the Plank cycle over the simple one highlighted assuming the same outlet temperature at the gas coolers (Section 2) decreases when the comparison is performed at finite and equal exchange area for the heat rejection. The simple cycle can, in fact, take advantage of the added area to reduce the approach at the end of the heat rejection phase below 1°C while, after the main gas cooler, the Plank cycle temperature difference to the ambient $\Delta T(3 - a)_p$ is greater than 5°C for $T_a = 30^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 8a).

Despite this, the Plank cycle improves COP by 4% - 12% and the cooling power by 8 - 18% for extreme ambient temperatures ($T_a = 45 - 60^\circ\text{C}$). It is worth noting that the increment in the cooling power is higher than the one expected from the thermodynamic simulations. This is partly associated to the impact that the system components have on the optimal thermodynamic cycle; additionally also the actual compressor volumetric efficiency plays a positive role in the Plank cycle due the minor compressor ratio resulting in a higher mass flow rate in the system.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Comparison between simple (s) and Plank (p) cycle, as a function of ambient temperature, with $k_s^{MGC} = 1.25$, $k_p^{MGC} = 1.00$, $k_p^{AGC} = 0.25$: (a) discharge pressures and approach temperature difference; (b) COP and cooling capacity.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Comparison between simple (s) and Plank (p) cycle, as a function of ambient temperature, with $k_s^{MGC} = 1.50$, $k_p^{MGC} = 1.00$, $k_p^{AGC} = 0.50$: (a) discharge pressures and approach temperature difference; (b) COP and cooling capacity.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Comparison between simple (s) and Plank (p) cycle, as a function of ambient temperature, with $k_s^{MGC} = 2.0$, $k_p^{MGC} = 1.00$, $k_p^{AGC} = 1.00$: (a) discharge pressures and approach temperature difference; (b) COP and cooling capacity.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The Plank cycle was proposed more than a century ago as a method to increase COP of the simple transcritical cycle. In view of adapting to rising temperatures and making CO₂ cycles efficient on a global scale, this paper critically analyses benefits and drawback of such a cycle.

While the thermodynamic analysis shows potential benefits when ideal components are considered, the introduction of compressor and pump efficiency give an insight on the working conditions optimisation.

From a technological point of view, this study shows how the supercritical pump is a key component: its regulation limits and its reliability under the operating conditions necessary for a Plank cycle must be proven to make this cycle a viable option.

When applied to a real test case, with finite heat transfer area for heat rejection, the Plank cycle demonstrates the impact of the Auxiliary Gas Cooler, which needs to be largely sized to guarantee benefits. Numerical simulations show a linear increase of COP from 0% to 12% for ambient temperature ranging from 30 to 60°C, when the Plank cycle is compared to a simple cycle using the same gas cooler. Cooling capacity increases with respect to the simple cycle in the same range of ambient temperature, from 0% to 18%.

Further work should include considerations on the control loops architecture and stability necessary to control the intermediate pressure and the sensitivity of the overall performances to small perturbation near the optimal working point. In addition, cost/benefit analysis of this system compared to other solutions (mechanical subcooling, adiabatic heat exchangers) and the possible synergies (Plank cycle might present positive synergy with ejectors, providing a higher-pressure stream to the motive of the ejector) is required.

In addition to these topics, the potential application of this cycle to heat pumps (or integrated heating/cooling systems) is worth evaluation. In particular, the rejection of the heat at two different pressure levels can find useful applications to promote the heat exchange on the sink side and the discontinuity on the refrigerant temperature profile to optimize the pinch point position dares investigation.

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